

THE SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCE OF THE FAMILY ON THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract: In this article, the reasons why we could not keep our health in time in our home, in the environment we are used to, as well as because we did not sufficiently form the knowledge and skills of a healthy lifestyle from an early age, are correct. opinions are presented

Keywords: Health, lifestyle, activity, illness, medical, respondent.

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Introduction. According to scientists and experts, there are five main conditions for a healthy lifestyle, which are, first of all, proper nutrition, physical activity, avoidance of harmful habits, proper organization of work and active rest, and hygienic is to practice skills. When it comes to our greatest wealth - health, it is necessary to analyze the opinions of scientists about the concept of "healthy lifestyle" that is often heard in our ears.

Of course, modern medical science has developed in Uzbekistan, and there are many noble people who are masters of their profession among medical workers. However, many people today know very well that if a person consciously organizes his lifestyle and does not stand against him on an equal footing with that doctor even when he gets sick, it will be difficult to overcome the pain. The health of a person who complies with these conditions will undoubtedly be in his own hands. But most of the time, following these conditions seems to be an achievement for young people. One of the main causes of illness and premature death among many people today is the fact that family members themselves are not trying to get healthy, there is still some miracle life-giving medicine or doctor. that they live believing that.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. But there are many young people who do not know this simple fact. One of the objective reasons for this is the fact that in the former Soviet era, medical services were free, and the demand for the qualifications of medical personnel was low. Although this policy served to reduce many diseases that occurred among the population in the initial periods of the old regime, at the same time, such a policy also created a feeling of indifference and lack of care in

people's health. Another reason is that the disease has been fought not by its cause, but by its consequences. As a result, more attention was paid to building hospitals and increasing the number of beds in them, and the field of propaganda was considered secondary. As a result, due to the low medical culture among the population, the disease continued to increase. It goes without saying that it had a negative impact on the budget of every family. As a result, it had a negative effect not only on the budget, but also on the strength of the family, and it still does.

It should be noted with special responsibility that the development of young families, which are the foundation of our country, to strengthen the foundation of our future, the promotion should be started first of all from the family, and moreover, from the neighborhood where "homeland is home" for all of us. Because if we establish a healthy lifestyle in the family, this family member will understand that health is the first priority. What is understood by one family is understood by other close relatives of this family - relatives, then brothers and sisters, and finally by relatives.

According to the results, 51.6% of human health depends on a healthy lifestyle, 20.5% on heredity, 19.3% on the external environment, and 8.6% on the health care system. It can be seen that health is directly related to how a person lives, what he eats, who he deals with, and how he can organize a decent and comfortable lifestyle for himself both at work and at rest.

Health is not only a healthy walk, but also a guarantee of a long life. Birth, growing up, reaching adulthood and working towards personal and universal interests, aging and death - these are the legitimate stages of a person's life. This requires understanding that the fight for life is the fight for health.

So, a healthy lifestyle is an effort of every person to have spiritual, mental, spiritual and physical qualities. If a person can put his life into an active mode of movement, can consciously determine the daily routine, can properly organize eating, working or resting routines, can refrain from harmful habits while observing the rules of hygiene, the environment if he has a culture of behavior that allows him to live peacefully with his family and neighbors and close relatives, and that he is primarily responsible for the birth of a healthy child if he understands, it can be said that he has ideas about a healthy lifestyle.

Today, a lot of attention is paid to health and a healthy lifestyle all over the world. For example, American scientists are more likely to associate them with aggressive behavior when asked what causes looking behind the curtain. That is, a person becomes belligerent, irritable, and impatient. This ultimately leads to drug addiction, alcoholism, unhealthy relationships between husband and wife, increasing prejudice against women, indifference to sports, and interpersonal conflicts.

So, there is a problem worth thinking about in our medical culture related to a healthy lifestyle.

Of course, the concept of a healthy lifestyle is formed in each person in a unique way. Respondents were asked "How do you understand a healthy lifestyle?" when asked the question, the majority, that is, about 41% of the respondents, associated it with "environmental cleanliness", 37.3% with "proper, ration-based nutrition", the rest - connected with "sleep on time", "do sports" (28.4%), "do not smoke, do not drink".

Of course, ideas related to such a healthy lifestyle are formed and, if necessary, nurtured. When studying where to get ideas about a healthy lifestyle, it became clear that the role and role of mass media is great. Especially women believe that television plays a big role (72.6%), newspapers - in second place - 57.5%, magazines - 46.3% and radio - 31.2%. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that the information and information from these sources are popular and popular, to pay special attention to the timely delivery of radio broadcasts and periodicals and magazines in the neighborhood. Therefore, the knowledge and ideas formed in each young generation about a healthy lifestyle and their transformation into conscious behavior in practical life make it possible to solve many social problems. That is why it is necessary to increase the efficiency of propaganda and propaganda work carried out among the people today, to make it a component of ideological and spiritual work.

Conclusion. All our efforts aimed at developing children's sports, which are gaining popularity in our independent country, introducing family sports into life in accordance with the characteristics of our national mentality, stabilizing a healthy lifestyle in a strong family, are in line with the strategy of our reforms, and contribute to peace, harmony and development in our country, youth contributes to the stability of families. It is natural that a number of good measures implemented in our country, including the practice of medical examination of brides and grooms for marriage, will have a very positive effect.

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